
IVF EVOLUTION IN UZBEKISTAN. FROM MULTIPLE EMBRYO TRANSFER ON DAY 3 TO ELECTIVE SINGLE EMBRO TRANSFER ON DAY 5 FOR BETTER NEONATAL OUTCOMES

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Study question:

Is the introduction of elective single embryo transfer (eSET) at the blastocyst stage viable as a standard of care in Uzbekistan?

Summary answer:

We abandoned the cleavage stage transfer of 2 or more embryos in favor of transferring a single high-quality blastocyst on day 5.

What is known already:

IVF was officially permitted in Uzbekistan in 2019. Initially, the culture of embryos until the cleavage stage (days 2 to 3) with the transfer of multiple embryos was chosen for its speed and simplicity. Low cleavage stage transfer implantation rates led to multiple embryo transfers to achieve an acceptable clinical pregnancy rate, resulting in multiple pregnancies. A higher implantation rate with blastocyst stage transfer allows for the implementation of elective single embryo transfer as a standard of care, maintaining the clinical pregnancy rate while increasing singleton pregnancies and offering a safer approach to assisted reproduction technology treatment.

Study design, size, duration:

We conducted a retrospective analysis, during which we tailed the embryo transfers for the years 2019 and 2023.

This approach allowed us to systematically examine and compare the outcomes of embryo transfer procedures in these years, based on available records and data.

Our study involved 848 women, encompassing a detailed retrospective analysis of data spanning 2019 and 2023.

Participants/materials, setting, methods:

The study involved patients aged 18-48, with an average age of 33.

The study was conducted in the first reproductive center, which is historically recognized as the first in vitro fertilization (IVF) clinic in our republic. Embryos grown in 2023 were cultured in the same incubator as in 2019 and HEPES medium was used for embryo transfer.

Main results and the role of chance:

The dynamics of embryo transfers changed from 2019 to 2023. The average number of transferred embryos decreased from 2.065 to 1.527, reflecting the shift towards a strategy of single embryo transfer. The analysis also revealed a shift in preferences between three-day and five-day embryos. In 2019, the ratio was 63% to 37% in favor of three-day embryos, whereas by 2023, these figures reduced to 5% to 95% in favor of five-day embryos, contributing to increased implantation efficiency.

Our retrospective analysis revealed a higher implantation rate with blastocyst-stage transfer (40%) compared to cleavage-stage transfer (22%). These changes in the embryo transfer strategy reflect the evolution of practices in Uzbekistan, emphasizing a more conscientious approach to the procedure and reducing obstetric and perinatal risks.

Implementing eSET required close collaboration with reproductive specialists and counseling patients to ensure an understanding of the benefits of eSET and the health risks of multiple pregnancies. Shifting to day 5 transfers necessitated a conceptual change from "each fertilized oocyte is to be transferred" to "embryos developed into blastocysts are to be transferred."

Limitations, reasons for caution:

In recent years, there has been an increase in the frequency of multiple pregnancies in Uzbekistan, likely associated with the widespread adoption of assisted

reproductive technologies (ART). The observed growth raises the question of whether all clinics providing ART services have transitioned to a single embryo transfer strategy.

Wider implications of the findings:

We propose to create a national guideline in reproductive medicine, based on the published data from other countries and on our research, with the limitation of the transfer of no more than two embryos at the blastocyst stage. This guideline's nationwide implementation shall reduce risks for both mother and child.